

CRM-GEOTHERMAL DELIVERABLE D6.2

PROJECT WEBSITE

Summary:

This deliverable describes the structure and objectives of the final project website of CRM-geothermal: <https://crm-geothermal.eu>. A website is set up to be a central hub for all outreach activities, providing up-to-date information about the project's aim and current status.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document describes the structure and objectives of the final project website of CRM-geothermal: <https://crm-geothermal.eu> (Figure 1). A website is set up to be a central hub for all outreach activities, providing up-to-date information about the project's aim and current status.

The website content has been drafted by EFG, and has been reviewed by the Coordinator and Project Partners.

For the development of the final website, a professional company has been subcontracted for the implementation of design and content elements envisioned by the Project Team.

Even though this is the final project website, it is expected to evolve during the project duration, and it will be kept continuously updated, tailored for the needs of the project.

Figure 1: CRM-geothermal website's front page.

2 PROJECT WEBSITE

The website content has been drafted from existing project descriptions, and formatted for website delivery. The content has first been reviewed by the WP4 and WP6 teams, and the Coordinator.

The initial content describes the Project Team (Figure 2), overall objectives, key messages, provides a news and event section, and contact and subscriptions forms. The website is available under the following link: <https://crm-geothermal.eu>

Figure 2: CRM-geothermal Project Partners.

Six website developers were contacted with a call for tenders to prepare the final design and content. EFG received three offers for implementation, and selected Leonnidas' (<http://leonnidas.com/>) offer, based on a best value for money principle.

The website developers were provided with the project stylebook, the funding reference requirements, and initial content. The initial design was shared with the project partners for review and feedback. After two rounds of feedback and improvements, the project developers have finalised the website, including the implementation of responsive design, suitable for different screen sizes.

3 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Even though the final website design was presented at the end of October, 2022, the website is expected to receive content updates throughout the implementation of the project. News posts will describe project activities and events. Media information will include project brochures, press releases and other dissemination content. The events calendar will be updated with relevant events in the raw material and geothermal sector.